

Enhancing Marine Biological Observations with the resilience of National Coastal Communities (EMBORNCC) to climate change with essential Fisherman aid and a Nautical Border Alert System

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Abstract:

Technology in today's world become more sensitive and productive with various aspects of socialization. Internet of Things (IoT) platform used to excavate and solve many of the sophisticated problems with limited resources and less infrastructure. The real life problems can be considered under IoT technology by the help of various sensors and technical binds including RFID, Artificial Intelligence, device connectivity and communication etc. This article provides a good framework for increasing the fisherman productivity used in Sultanate of Oman, the part of Arabian Peninsula. This AI based proposal can provide a good alert system for fishermen during 24/7-time frame. This may use various sensor based setup and artificial intelligence mechanism to detect the availability of various fishes while fishing. Adverse climate conditions, unawareness of sea border always creates problems to the fishermen. The problems of fishermen including accidents met with obstacles and other yachts, yachts stuck due to insufficient fuels, crucial leakage etc. These cases happened while searching for quality fishes in various marine plots. The suggested framework can initiate solution of the said issues and saves the life of fishermen. Here the system uses IoT Patrolling robot along with Black box. This system has Ultrasonic sensors and GPS which may alert the fisherman about marine boundaries. Though the framework handles the rain alert system by the help of temperature sensors and it helps to locate quality fish by evaluating the *ph* values and other water monitoring measurements. Fuel tank measures and boat leakage might be recorded and the same can be reported to both patrolling robot and fishermen yacht. The system has Twilio messaging system to enable all the communication states. The framework provides sensor values updated to the cloud using ThingSpeak.com platform.

Keywords: IoT, RFID, Artificial Intelligence, Ultrasonic sensors, GPS, pH values, GoPiGo Robot